

PROSPECTS AND APPLICATION OF USING SECONDARY RESOURCES IN THE PRODUCTION OF GASO-CONCRETE

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Abstract. *The article describes the increasing accumulation of industrial waste and the importance of waste processing, as well as the study of the composition of waste sand with peroxynite, the preparation of aerated concrete samples, and the study of physical and mechanical properties of the laboratory of JizPI "Construction Materials and Structures" department.*

Keywords: *peroxynite, sand, aerated concrete, modulus of elasticity, degree of porosity, oxide, thermal conductivity coefficient.*

Today, the rapid development of the construction industry requires the production of low-cost, energy-efficient construction materials and products. In this regard, it remains urgent to find an effective solution for the production of construction materials and products with the processing of industrial and household waste, which is constantly accumulating.

Scientific work and test-research are being carried out in the way of industrial waste processing, and positive results are being obtained. Currently, the need for environmentally friendly, non-flammable, long-term thermal insulation materials is increasing in the field of construction and engineering. These requirements are met by silicate materials with a porous macrostructure, such as foam glass, foam concrete, aerated concrete, foam silicate, and porous glass ceramic [1].

The most rational direction of disposal of industrial waste, i.e. disposal, is to obtain various products for construction purposes and use them as man-made raw materials. The most important resource-saving source in construction is the extensive use of secondary material resources, which are production and consumption waste. The amount of industrial waste is growing faster than the total production. On average, 8-10% of the cost of basic products is spent only on their destruction and storage[1].

In the laboratory of the "Construction Materials and Structures" Department of Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, scientific research is being carried out on the production of construction materials based on industrial waste. Heat-insulating structural aerated concrete was chosen as the object of research, and the physical-mechanical properties of the prepared aerated concrete sample, such as volumetric mass, brand, compressive strength, heat transfer coefficient and thermal resistance, were determined in modern equipment. The bulk modulus and fineness level of peroxynite waste sand determined using electronic calculation software are presented in the following table.

Also, peroxynite waste from the "Koytash" tungsten mine located in the Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region was taken as a filler in the production of aerated concrete. Determination of the particle composition of peroxynite sand was carried out in laboratory sieves according to the

established procedure, and it was found that the bulk modulus of peroxynite sand is 1.96, it is very fine sand according to the requirements of GOST 31424-2010.

Table 1

Qumning massasi	$M_{2,5}$	$M_{1,25}$	$M_{0,63}$	$M_{0,315}$	$M_{0,16}$	d_{10}
1000	24	79	25	59.8	25.4	20
HISOBLASH						

$a_{2,5}$	$a_{1,25}$	$a_{0,63}$	$a_{0,315}$	$a_{0,16}$	d_{10}
2.4	7.9	2.5	59.8	25.4	2

$A_{2,5}$	$A_{1,25}$	$A_{0,63}$	$A_{0,315}$	$A_{0,16}$	d_{10}
2.4%	10.3%	12.8%	72.6%	98%	100%

Qumning yiriklik moduli	Qumning guruhi
1.96	Juda mayda qum

The table shows the names and percentages of oxides detected in peroxynite waste

Table 2

№	Name of oxides	Oxide amount, percentage
1	Silicon di oxides	41-48%
2	Potassium oxides	0,5-0,9%
3	Sodium oxides	0,9-1,4 %
4	Calcium oxide	19-22 %
5	Magnesium oxides	0,8-1,2%
6	Umumium carbon	2,0-3,35%
7	Aluminum oxide	3,7-5,0%
8	Common iron	8-12%
9	General gold and sulfur	0,3-1,0 %
10	Phosphorus was oxides	0,05-0,07%
11	Titanium oxides	0,1 %
12	Manganese	0,8-1,3%
13	Miss	0,01-0,02 %
14	Movement	0,02-0,03 %
15	Lead	0,08-0,013 %
16	Висмут	0,005-0,009%
17	Arsenic	0,01-0,02%
18	Tungsten oxides	0,01-0,1 %
19	Toblanishdagi zhotysh (P.P.P.)	7-15%

A sample of aerated concrete 300x300x100 mm in size was prepared in laboratory conditions without autoclave using selected peroxynite sand, PTs 450 brand Huaxin cement and gas generating components as filler. After solidification of the aerated concrete poured into the mold, two samples of 300x300x40 mm size were prepared, and the thermal conductivity and thermal resistance of the aerated concrete sample were determined on XND-2-3030C equipment.

Figure 1. The process of compressing aerated concrete samples in a UTEST hydraulic press.

The 28-day strength of the aerated concrete sample was determined in the UTEST hydraulic press manufactured in Turkey. According to the results, the average compressive strength of the aerated concrete sample made of peroxynite sand was determined to be 1.33 MPa.

Figure 2. Determination of heat transfer coefficient and thermal resistance of aerated concrete sample on XND-2-3030C equipment.

It was determined that the coefficient of thermal conductivity of the aerated concrete sample is 0.139 W/m K, and the thermal resistance is 0.21 m² K/W in XND-2-3030C equipment. It should be noted that the humidity level of this aerated concrete sample was 18.0% during the test. It is known that high humidity has a negative effect on the thermal conductivity of the material.

In the requirements of the standard, the coefficient of thermal conductivity of the dry aerated concrete sample of D600 brand is 0.14 W/m K; and in the case of 4% humidity, the K coefficient indicator is set at 0.16 W/m.

According to the test results, the heat transfer coefficient of the aerated concrete sample fully meets the standard requirements.

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